

CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM WIRES

M. Doktor¹, J. Blucher², and H.P. Degischer¹

¹ *Institute of Materials Science, Vienna University of Technology
Karlsplatz 13/E308, A-1040 Vienna, Austria*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Northeastern University Boston
360 Huntington Avenue, Boston, Massachusetts 02115, USA*

SUMMARY: With a continuous infiltration process fiber reinforced aluminum wires with 1.5mm outside diameter, lengths up to 200m and volume fractions of 35 to 60% have been successfully produced. As reinforcement different ceramic fibers like Nextel 610, Nextel 440 and Altex and also carbon fibers, Thornel P-25, have been used. The matrix material is aluminum. Investigations of the cross section with optical and scanning electron microscope show high infiltration quality and a good fiber distribution. The tensile strengths of all ceramic fiber reinforced wires are within the expectations from the rule of mixture (ROM). For the carbon fiber reinforced composite wires even higher values were measured. From dynamic three point bending tests Young's module within or slightly below the ROM prediction were found. The electric conductivity is dominated by the matrix material, even the carbon fibers do not contribute.

KEYWORDS: continuous fibers, gas pressure infiltration, aluminum matrix composites

INTRODUCTION

The reinforcement of aluminum by continuous fibers (ceramic or carbon) results in a unique material that combines the ductile nature of the metallic matrix with the high strength and stiffness of the fibers. The thermal expansion can be reduced to almost zero [1]. Also the hot strength compared to the matrix material is significantly improved.

To overcome the non-wetting conditions existing between reinforcement and liquid metal some energy has to be applied. A common method is pressure infiltration either by gas or mechanically applied pressure (squeeze casting) [2,3]. Both methods are limited with respect to the sample size by the dimensions of the pressure vessel and the mold. Long contact time between reinforcement and molten metal can lead to brittle reaction products forming at the fiber matrix interface. Consequently only a fraction of the theoretical strength potential of fiber reinforced aluminum may be achieved [4-6].

A newly developed continuous gas pressure infiltration process is capable to infiltrate endless fibers with molten aluminum, i.e. fiber reinforced aluminum wire can be produced in a continuous way (in the future may be even simple profiles). The production rate for this process is up to 15m/min and the contact time fiber/molten metal is less than a second. So the formation of interface reaction products can be considerably suppressed [1,7].

EXPERIMENTAL

Continuous Infiltration

Fig. 1 shows a schematic sketch of the process route developed at Northeastern University, Boston. This process can be used to produce metal-matrix composite wires with various combinations of metal matrices and reinforcements. In a joint effort the production parameters for the chosen combinations were developed.

Fig. 1: Continuous Infiltration Process

The fibers are fed through an infiltration chamber where the gas pressure is applied. During the infiltration process the pulling speed of the fibers and thus of the wire can be varied from 1 to 15 m/min, i.e. the infiltration time is changing from 1.3 to 0.2 seconds with increasing pulling speed. The diameter of the reinforced aluminum wire is controlled by an orifice system [7].

Table 1: Overview of matrix/fiber combinations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Matrix	h.p. Al	h.p. Al	h.p. Al	AlMg0.2	AlMg0.6	AlMg0.7	h.p. Al
Fiber	Nextel 440	Nextel 610	Altex	Altex	Altex	Altex	Thornel P-25

For the investigations presented in this paper wires with matrix/fiber combinations according to Table 1, an outside diameter of about 1.5 mm and lengths up to 200 m were fabricated.

The volume fraction of the fibers was in the range of 35 to 60%. Table 2 shows some properties of the starting materials.

Table 2: fiber / matrix properties

Property	Nextel 440	Nextel 610	Altex	Thornel P-25	h.p.Al
Composition [wt%]	70 Al ₂ O ₃ 28 SiO ₂ 2 B ₂ O ₃	> 99 Al ₂ O ₃ 0.2-0.3 SiO ₂ 0.4-0.7 Fe ₂ O ₃	85 Al ₂ O ₃ 15 SiO ₂ <0.05 impurities	>97 C	99.99
Density [g/cm ³]	not reported	3.8-3.9	3.3	1.9	2.7
Diameter [μm]	~12	10	15	~11	
Tensile Strength ^{*)} [MPa]	2060	2400-2800	1800	1380	100
Young's Mod. [GPa]	186	380	210	159	70

Characterization Methods

The infiltration quality was checked by optical metallography where the fiber distribution and possible pores can be seen. Fracture surfaces were investigated by SEM and for the system h.p. Al/ Thornel P-25 even TEM specimens have been prepared [8].

For all matrix/fiber combinations listed in Table 1 tensile tests were performed. The tensile specimens were 102 mm long with a gauge length of 25 mm. The ends were fixed with epoxy adhesive in a steel tube. All tests were performed at room temperature using a standard Instron machine with a speed rate of 0.375 mm/min. Because the strain gage was slipping during the tensile test the Young's modulus was determined by a dynamic three point bending test with a TA Instruments - DMA 2980 device. This method is usually used for plastics, but the obtained results are very convincing. As another advantage of this equipment the properties can easily be measured within a temperature range of -145 to +600°C. For the performed dynamic bending tests a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 50 μm were chosen. The support distance is 50 mm. Although tests within the temperature range of -40 to +400°C were done with a heating rate of 2 K/min. Actually the dynamic test provides a complex modulus. But the storage modulus (real part of the complex modulus) is more or less equivalent with the Young's modulus obtained from a tensile test [9].

Fig. 2: Micrographs at different magnifications showing a typical cross section of h.p.Al/Thornel P-25 wire (left – whole cross section)

^{*)} measured on impregnated strands

To evaluate the aluminum carbide content for h.p. Al/Thornel P-25, the composite was dissolved in sodium hydroxide. The developed gas volume was measured and then analyzed in a gas chromatograph. Knowing the mass of the sample and the hydrogen and methane content of the gas, the aluminum and aluminum carbide content can be calculated [1]. The electric resistance was measured with an ‘Milli-TO2 0.1mΩ – 2x10¹⁴Ω, Dr. Kamphausen’s equipment for lengths of 0.5 to 1.6 m.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optical metallography of the composite wire show a good fiber distribution and that the fibers are well infiltrated with no pores (Fig. 2).

In Fig. 3 the tensile test results are plotted for the different matrix/fiber/volume fractions. The obtained results are in the range of the rule of mixture (ROM) prediction for the ceramic fibers. Only the composite with the carbon fiber (Thornel P-25) shows values significantly higher than one would expect from the ROM. Due to the high reactivity of carbon with molten aluminum a clear decrease of the tensile strength with increasing infiltration time can be seen (Fig. 4)[1].

Fig. 3: Tensile strength for different matrix/fiber/volume fraction combinations

The results from the dynamic three point bending tests for the composite wires are compared with aluminum and steel reference specimens (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6). Fig. 5 shows the average Young’s module measured from three different specimens. Each specimen was measured four times with a turn of 90° after each measurement (the fifths would be again the starting position). Because the cross section of the wire is not perfect circular and the fibers are not always evenly distributed there is a relative big scattering. There is almost perfect correlation

between the results for the aluminum and steel reference specimens with data from literature, e.g. [10].

Fig. 4: Correlation of the tensile strength and the carbide content with the infiltration time for h.p.Al/Thornel P-25

Fig. 5: Young's modulus measured with dynamic three point bending test (room temperature)

Fig. 6 shows the temperature dependence of the Young's modulus for one specific specimen where the temperature ranges from -40 to $+400^{\circ}\text{C}$. Due to the beginning of plastic deformation at temperatures higher than 120°C (even for an amplitude as low as $5\mu\text{m}$) the modulus for the aluminum specimen is plotted for -40 to 120°C only.

Fig. 6: Temperature dependence of the Young's modulus measured by dynamic three point bending test

In Fig. 7 the results of the electric conductivity measurement are plotted. Due to the fact that even the carbon fibers (Thornel P-25) have a conductivity 500 times worse than that of pure aluminum the conductivity of the composite is mainly determined by the volume fraction of the fibers. The electric conductivity is although lowered by any alloying element added to the h.p. Al matrix.

CONCLUSION

With the continuous infiltration process high quality MMC wires could be produced. The achieved infiltration quality is very good in spite of the short infiltration time. This short fiber/melt contact time enabled a surprisingly strong reduction of carbide formation (h.p.Al/Thornel P-25). So one can take advantage of the full potential carbon fibers offer for optimizing the strength and stiffness properties. In addition carbon fibers are significantly cheaper than ceramic fibers. Batches of 200m infiltrated aluminum wire were achieved limited only by the amount of aluminum in the infiltration chamber.

A potential application of such wires could be high tension cables, exhibiting high specific strength, low thermal expansion and high electric conductivity. The continuous process promises an economic mass production.

Fig. 7: Electrical conductivity of different composite wires (Al 99.98 – 37.6m/Ωmm²)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge a scholarship from the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Vienna University of Technology, allowing a stay of M. Doktor at Northeastern University Boston.

REFERENCES

1. Doktor M., Blucher J. and Degischer H.P., "Carbon Fiber Reinforced Aluminum Wires", *Proceedings of the 19th International SAMPE Europe Conference*, Paris, France, April 22-24,1998, pp. 555-564.
2. Suresh S., Mortensen A. and Needleman A., "Fundamentals of Metal-Matrix Composites", Butterworth-Heinemann, 1993.
3. Degischer H.P., Schulz P. and Lacom W., "Properties of Continuous Fibre Reinforced Al- and Mg-Matrix Composites Produced by Gas Pressure Infiltration", *Key Engineering Materials*, 1997, Vols. 127-131, pp. 99-110.
4. Degischer H.P., Schulz P., Lacom W. and Langgartner J., "Properties of Continuous Fibre Reinforced Aluminium Depending on the Infiltration Process and Local Fibre Variations", *Proc. 3rd Int. Symposium on Structural & Functional Gradient Materials/FGM'94*, Lausanne, Switzerland, Oct. 10-12,1994, pp.321-326.

5. Schmitt Th., Neuwirth E., Schulz P., Leitner H. and Degischer H.P., "Characterization of C/Al-Composites Produced by Gas Pressure Infiltration", *ICAA3*, Trondheim 1992, Vol.1, pp.441-446.
6. Lacom W., Degischer H.P. and Schulz P., "Assessment and Control of Surface Reactions of Carbon Fibres in Light Weight Metal Matrix Composites", *Key Engineering Materials*, 1997, Vols. 127-131, pp.679-686.
7. Blucher J.T. and Doktor M., "A new pressure Infiltration Process for Continuous Production of Fiber Reinforced MMC Structural Elements", *Proceedings of the 30th International SAMPE Technical Conference*, San Antonio, Texas, Oct. 22-24, 1998, pp. 442-449.
8. Pippel E., Woltersdorf J., Doktor M., Blucher J. and Degischer H.P., "Interlayer Structure of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Aluminium Wires", in review.
9. Ehrensteiner G.W., Riedel G. and Trawiel P., "Praxis der Thermischen Analyse von Kunststoffen", Hanser Verlag, 1998, p.164.
10. Beitz W. and Küttner K.-H., "Dubbel – Taschenbuch für den Maschinenbau", 15th ed. Springer - Verlag, 1983, p.1375.